

0/4

Specialist

Knowledge Liberator

3

1

Champions the free sharing of research findings. They work as scholarly communications librarians or Open Access policy advisors.

Collects Open Scholarly Communications credits equal to level

2

Role

0/4

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Role

0/4

Specialist

Code Conjurer

3

1

Expert at creating and maintaining research software. They are research software engineers, software stewards, software developers, scientific programmers or research programmers.

Collects Open Research Software credits equal to level

2

Role

0/4

Specialist

Code Conjurer

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Expert at creating and maintaining research software. They are research software engineers, software stewards, software developers, scientific programmers or research programmers.

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Role

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Specialist

Data Wizard

3

1

The master of organizing and making sense of information. They are data stewards, data managers, data engineers or research data specialists.

**Collects FAIR data credits
equal to level**

2

Role

0/4

Specialist

Data Wizard

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1

The master of organizing and making sense of information. They are data stewards, data managers, data engineers or research data specialists.

**Collects FAIR data credits
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equal to level**

2

Role

0/4

Specialist

Public Engagement Guru

3

→

Excels at involving the general public in scientific research. They are outreach coordinators, science communicators or citizen science project managers

**Collects Citizen Science
credits equal to level**

2

Role

0/4

Specialist

Public Engagement Guru

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→

Excels at involving the general public in scientific research. They are outreach coordinators, science communicators or citizen science project managers

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**Collects Citizen Science
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Role

2/6

Discovery Driver

5

3

Drives forward new discoveries and innovations. The traditional academic researcher role across various disciplines

Collaborates with Specialists and Generalists for points equal to level, +1 per collaborator

4

Discovery Driver

2/6

Discovery Driver

5

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Discovery Driver

0/4

Generalist

Transparency Champion

3

→

Advocates for openness across all aspects of research. They are open science policy advisors, open science programme officers, or research integrity officers.

Can collect max 1 credit per type, total up to level

2

Role

0/4

Generalist

Transparency Champion

3

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Advocates for openness across all aspects of research. They are open science policy advisors, open science programme officers, or research integrity officers.

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Can collect max 1 credit per type, total up to level

2

Role

0/4

Generalist

Social Glue

3

Builds and nurtures research communities. They are community managers, research network coordinators or community engagement officers.

→

Can add others' specialists \leq level to collabs in 1 turn. Gives 1 credit collected > 1 to collaborator. Does not collect own credits

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Role

0/4

Generalist

Social Glue

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2

Role

Event

We've got data at home

European funders
reward the reuse of
FAIR data

11

7

7

7

Event

Event

Out of Office: Open Science Festival

Two team members (generalist or specialist) are out of office on your first turn.

Level up these team members for free at the beginning of the second turn

8

8

8

8

Event

Event

**Taylor Swift endorses
Open Science on
social media**

Finally, the recognition
we deserve.

12

12

12

12

Event

Event

National Day for Research Software

An event on the importance of good, open research software.

If you have a code conjurer, it's unavailable in your first turn.

7

11

7

7

Event

Event

We found some spare FTE!

Draw a team member for free at the beginning of your turn. Start your turn as normal.

6

6

6

6

Event

Event

Major Squeeze

Major funding cut-backs.

Lose one role card.

3

3

3

3

Event

Event

Breaking Bad

Citizen Science receives awareness.

7

7

7

11

Event

Event

**Out of Office:
Conference**

You can't use your Discovery Driver this round.

Level up your Discovery Driver.

Event

Event

Metamorphic agreement

The university spends an obscene amount of money on an Open Access deal with a major scientific publisher.

3

3

8

3

Event

Event

**Recognition
&
Rewards**

I like what you did there.

8

8

8

8

Event

Event

PAYWALL

Subscribe to see this
card.

8

8

4

8

Event

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

0

total research
credits

10

30

20

40

**total research
credits**

50

70

09

0

total research
credits

10

30

20

40

**total research
credits**

50

70

09

0

total research
credits

10

30

20

40

**total research
credits**

50

70

09

0

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credits

10

30

20

40

**total research
credits**

50

70

09

0

total research
credits

10

30

20

40

**total research
credits**

50

70

09

**open scholarly
communications
resources**

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

10

11

12

**citizen science &
societal engagement
resources**

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

10

11

12

**open research
software resources**

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

10

11

12

FAIR data resources

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

10

11

12

How to play “Open Science Alliance”

Objective: Collect the most research credits over 6 rounds.

Setup

Players start with:

- 2 red research credits counter cards (1 tens, 1 singles) set to zero
- A research team, consisting of:
 - 1 Discovery Driver (DD) (Level 2),
 - 1 Specialist of choice (Level 0),
 - 1 randomly drawn Role (Level 0).

Players place their research team face up on the table in front of them.

Shuffle Event and Role decks (excluding DDs) separately. Draw six Event cards and place as a deck face down in the center of the table. The remaining Event cards are not used during this game. Place the Role card deck face down next to the Event card deck. Place the eight Resource counter cards in the center of the table.

Per round, resources are tracked by overlaying the four types of Resource counter cards so that the numbers that are showing match the resource levels on the Event card.

Resource Counter cards
slide up to take resources

The four Resource types are FAIR data (**green**), open research software (**purple**), citizen science and societal engagement (**yellow**) and open scholarly publishing (**blue**).

Gameplay (6 Rounds)

A new round starts by revealing an Event card and setting resource levels on the Resource Counter cards. All players should obey any additional restrictions imposed by that round's Event card.

In the first round, the player who has had the longest research support staff title begins. Players continue to take turns clockwise.

The round ends when the resources of **two** types are depleted. The first turn passes clockwise after a round. Unused resources from previous rounds are discarded.

End of the game

After 6 rounds the player with most Research Credits wins.

During a turn, players get to

- Upskill (1a) or Hire (1b) and
 - Collect resources
- 1a. Upskilling (choose ONE of the following three)
- Increase one Role by 2 levels (turn 1 role card 180°)
 - Increase two Roles by 1 level each (turn 2 role cards 90°)
 - Increase Discovery Driver by 1 (turn 90°)

role card levels
turn to upskill (here
from 0 to 1)

A card should be oriented so that its current level is the number farthest from the player.

The Maximum levels are **4** for **Specialists/Generalists** and **6** for the **Discovery Driver**

1b. Hire

If not upskilling, hire a new team member: draw a card from the Role deck. New team members start at level 0.

2. Collect Resources

Players can collect resources once during their turn.

When collecting resources, players slide the central resource counter cards down and receive personal Research Credits equal to the total number of resources consumed (slide card up). They can choose to do this in one of two ways:

a. Independent Action

A single Specialist or Transparency Champion can turn resources into Research Credits equal to their level:

- Specialists can only collect resources of their type
- Transparency Champions can collect up to 1 resource of each type

b. Discovery Driver (DD) Collaboration

Discovery Drivers can't collect resources themselves.

Instead, they can invite other roles to collaborate. This allows each specialist in the collaboration to collect their own type of resource up to their respective level.

On top of that, one bonus resource is collected per invited collaborator. Specialists collect a collaboration bonus resource according to their type.

Rules for a successful collaboration:

- The combined levels of specialists and generalists in a collaboration must meet or exceed the level of the DD (**see example on the next rule card**).
- The total resources to be collected must be available in the shared resource pool of that round. This **includes** bonus resources. If not enough resources are available, **the collaboration can not occur**.
- The total number of base research credits (before collaboration bonuses) collected as a result of the collaboration must not exceed the level of the DD. If the combined levels of the collaborators exceed the level of the DD, the player decides how many of each resource type they collect so that the level of the DD is matched.

Rules for generalists in collaborations:

- **Transparency Champions** collect up to 1 resource of each type.
- **Social Glue** can include ONE other player's specialist of choice in the collaboration on that turn. Social Glue does not collect its own resources. If the resources collected thanks to Social Glue exceed 1, the player passes 1 of that resource to the player who owns the specialist card.

DD level 2

Code
Conjurer
level 1

Transparency
Champion
level 1

An example of a successful collaboration. The levels of the role cards (both at level 1, $1+1=2$) equal the DD's level (2).

In this example, the following Research Credits MUST be collectable:

- **1 open research software resource** for the Code Conjurer
- **1 resource of choice** for the Transparency Champion.
- **Collaboration bonus points:**
 - 1 open research software resource for the Code Conjurer
 - 1 resource of choice for the Transparency Champion

The total Research Credits collected will be equal to DD level + 1 bonus point for each collaborator (excluding DD, including level 0 collaborators).

Result: The player receives 4 Research Credits. Open software resources go down by 2 and 2 central resources of their choice go down by 1.